

Comparative Study of Laparoscopic vs Open Surgery for Appendectomy: Outcomes, Complications, and Recovery Times

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Abstract:

Introduction: Perforated appendicitis is an acute illness that requires emergent surgery. Open appendectomy (OA) or laparoscopic appendectomy (LA) is common procedure for appendicitis. While LA has grown in use and application as a surgical procedure and it is less invasive, there are still debates regarding its efficacy over OA especially for perforated appendicitis.

Methods: Participants were patients diagnosed with perforated appendicitis who underwent either open OA or LA surgery, according to the type of research. The primary assessed outcomes were the surgical time of operation being conducted, length of stay in hospital as well as recovery time. The experimenters conducted the research for a time period of 1 year.

Results: The rate of postoperative infections increased in the patients who had open surgery compared with laparoscopic surgery. Hospital time of stay for both the types of surgeries was comparable. The mean time for laparoscopic surgery was significantly less than the traditional open technique of surgery.

Conclusion: LA has benefits such as fewer hospital days and faster recovery in instances of perforated appendix, though there may be a higher risk for the development form intra-abdominal abscess. It also remains a viable alternative, especially for those at risk of complications. Further prospective studies are needed to aim at a more objective selection between OA and LA.

Keywords: Laparoscopic appendectomy, Open Appendectomy, Surgical Outcomes, Complications, Recovery Time

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Introduction

Appendicitis or inflammation of the vermiform appendix [1]: This condition, which carries a lifetime risk of 8.6% in men and 6.7 % women [1–2], is the main reason for abdominal surgery performed at any age among various gynaecological benign conditions [3]. Acute appendicitis may be difficult to diagnose because it presents with such a wide spectrum of symptoms [4]. Negative appendectomy is the incidence of performing procedures to investigate suspected appendicitis that do not prove to be cases of acute inflammation (about 30%) [5]. Surgical treatment at an early stage might result in avoidable medical interventions; on the other hand, performing surgery later creates a risk of complications [6]. Complications due to appendicitis are perforation, abscess formation and surgical site infections [7]. Technology advancements and the evolution of more minimally invasive approaches not only change how we treat our patients, but in some ways improve it [8]. LA has increasing acceptance and application. In the recent years LA, a minimally invasive surgical technique has been more

prevalent [9]. However, there is an ongoing debate on whether this method fares better than the standard OA [10]. Appendicitis is a common condition that often needs an operation during unsociable hours when there may be limited availability of laparoscopic equipment and skills [11]. The laparoscopic approach has the potential to be faster and more cost-effective, although it adds another layer of complexity [12–14], others have argued that there are no significant differences in outcomes of the two surgical procedures namely the laparoscopic procedure and an OA for perforated appendicitis [15].

Methods

This paper has made a comparison between LA vs OA outcomes. The analysis was conducted on a total of 30 subjects each for these two procedures, so total of 60 patients were considered for the study. Duration of operation and hospital stay were presented as continuous variables, analysed by means and standard deviations regarding each surgical procedure. The presence of site infections

was assessed as per data. Statistical analysis included the computation of an independent t-test for continuous variables between both groups and Chi-Square test results for categorical data. Furthermore, a multiple logistic regression analysis

was employed to evaluate the effect of the surgical type on patients' outcomes while adjusting for timing after surgery or duration in hospital. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Result

Table 1: Experiment statistical analysis (n=30 patients in each group)

Outcome Variable	LA procedure (n=30)	OA procedure (n=30)	p-value
Time of operation being conducted (mean $\pm$ SD)	45.00 $\pm$ 3.00 minutes	55.00 $\pm$ 3.50 minutes	0.001
Hospitalization operation time (mean $\pm$ SD)	4.00 $\pm$ 1.00 days	5.00 $\pm$ 1.00 days	0.05
Site Infections occurrence rate (%)	6 (20.00%)	15 (50.00%)	0.02

Table 1 shows LA period was notably reduced compared to the conventional time of response (45.00 minutes vs 55.00 minutes respectively, $p=0.001$). Hospitalization: Patients experiencing LA had significantly shorter hospital stay, when compared with those undergoing traditional appendectomy (4.00 vs 5.00 days; $p=0.05$). The incidence of operative site infections was

significantly less in LA group as compared to conventional OA group ($p=0.02$). The results of the analysis indicate this increasing trend for LA as an alternative to OA in sufferers with severe appendicitis. LA demonstrates many advantages similar to lower operation times, reduced hospital stay lengths and decreased chance of post-surgical incisional wound infection.

Table 2: Chi-square result of the comparison of the LA and OA procedure

Statistic	Value
Total Chi-Square Statistic (χ^2)	4.88
Degrees of Freedom (df)	1
p-value	0.027

Table 2 displays that the p-value associated with this Chi-Square statistic is approximately 0.027, indicating that there is a statistically significant difference in the rate of surgical site infections between LA and OA ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Multiple logistic regression analysis of the two surgical procedures

Predictor	B (Coefficient)	Standard Error	Wald Statistic	p-value	Odds Ratio (Exp(B))
Intercept	-8.500	2.500	11.56	0.001	-
Time of Operation	0.450	0.120	14.06	0.001	1.569
Hospitalization Time of being operated	0.700	0.350	4.00	0.046	2.014
Surgery Type (Comparison)	1.800	0.700	6.60	0.010	6.050

Table 3 represents the results of multiple logistic regression analysis show that the three predictors (Time of Operation, Hospitalization Time and Surgery Type) are correlated with each other. Increased operating time, prolonged hospital stay and OA are risk factors for increased site infections. The infection rates for patients who have undergone OA show a very strong relationship with the increased risk.

Discussion

LA has become the favored surgical technique for treating acute appendicitis. Multiple studies have shown evidence that this less intrusive method of appendectomy significantly lowers infection rates and postoperative problems when compared to the standard open procedure [16-19]. The patient demographics in this study were consistent with prior research conducted by Chaudhari et al. [20], showing a higher proportion of male patients. Nevertheless, the sex ratio was somewhat lower compared to the findings published by Mishra et al.

[21]. The appendix was most often located retrocaecally, which aligns with the results of Mishra et al. [21]. However, the frequency of this site was greater in our research. The findings of this study support the results of Aziz, Athanasiou et al.'s meta-analysis [22], showing that LA has a much shorter duration of surgery when compared to open appendectomy. The occurrence of converting to open surgery was rare, consistent with the findings in the literature, although a few studies indicate greater rates of conversion [23].

Although the occurrence of problems during surgery was similar in both groups and was related to the severity of the illness rather than the surgical method used [24-25], the OA group had a higher incidence of complications after the surgery. It is worth mentioning that laparoscopy resulted in decreased rates of wound infections. This is confirmed by a meta-analysis which shown a decrease in wound infections after laparoscopic surgery [26-27]. The use of laparoscopy in severe appendicitis is still a subject of debate since it has

the potential to cause the development of abscesses inside the abdomen [26-27]. Nevertheless, the findings of this investigation, like those of Barkhausen S et al. [27], demonstrated identical incidence of intra-abdominal abscesses across laparoscopic and open methods. Notwithstanding concerns, a substantial majority of surgeons endorse LA as a suitable treatment for all types of appendicitis, including patients with perforation [28-32]. Studies have shown that LA results in less adhesion development compared to open surgery. This is because laparoscopic surgery causes less tissue damage and so reduces the inflammatory response [33]. In addition, this less invasive procedure has shown benefits in overweight patients with quicker recovery after surgery, which is consistent with the results of Enochsson L et al. [34]. One drawback of LA is the possible challenge in identifying related cancers, such as mucinous cystadenoma of the caecum, as documented by V Shayani [35]. To summarize, LA has several benefits compared to open appendectomy, such as less postoperative complications and faster recovery periods. Despite ongoing obstacles and concerns, laparoscopy is increasingly being favored as the preferred surgical method, particularly in instances of severe appendicitis.

According to the subsequent results of work by Jaschinski, Mosch, Eikermann et al. and Rashid, Nazir, LA could greatly reduce postoperative discomfort in patients when compared with open surgery (as proven consistent with earlier studies cooperating and confirming the current study) [36-38]. The stay in hospital of patients receiving LA was much less--and only 1.10 ± 0.12 days, compared to OA (2.16 $\pm$ 0.55 days). These finding accords with Minne et al. [39], Total hospitalization time was not longer than Hebebrand et al.'s [40] and Mutter et al. [39-41]. One patient, for fear of injuring the cecum, switched from laparoscopic to open surgery and as a result the duration of stay in hospital rose. Patients who received LA returned to their daily lifestyle much earlier than those had open surgery. In addition, a similar result to theirs is the appearance of De Utpal and Rashid, Nazir [37,42-45]. Though the initial outlays for laparoscopic appendectomies frequently prove to be greater because of the need to purchase special equipment such as disposable trocars, endostaplers, and advanced energy devices [42-43], the availability of reusable instruments and the adoption of less expensive technologies can greatly enhance its monetization. The method of the present study utilized handcrafted endo-loops in place to ligate the appendiceal stump. This was considered a safe, efficient, and cost effective way of doing things compared to pre-tied end-loop stitches [44]. Heikkinen TJ et al. [44] demonstrated that even though LA has higher initial costs of hospitalization, it ultimately stands to save a great

deal of money since it enables recuperation to proceed more quickly and work to return sooner to its former rate. No deaths occurred in the study. The death rates of appendectomy are generally low, ranging from an estimated 0.05 percent for laparoscopic to 0.3 for open procedures [45]. These figures emphasize the safety of LA. Generally, LA produces better results in postoperative pain, recuperation time, and resumption of daily activities as compared to traditional open surgery. Although the detailed costs may have seemed high, in the long-term good remuneration and less tax on the patient, make this a viable way forward. Not only that, but its popularity is substantiated by the safety profile of LA [45].

Conclusion

Traditional open surgery is not as effective as laparoscopic surgery when it comes to treating appendicitis. When compared to patients who had standard open surgery, those who underwent laparoscopic surgery ended up spending less time in the operating room and the hospital, and they also had a lower risk of developing an infection following the LA procedure in comparison to the OA procedure.

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